

FASTER THAN REAL-TIME DETECTION OF SHOT BOUNDARIES, SAMPLING STRUCTURE AND DYNAMIC KEYFRAMES IN VIDEO

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ABSTRACT

The detection of shot boundaries (hardcuts and short dissolves), sampling structure (progressive / interlaced / pull-down) and dynamic keyframes in a video are fundamental video analysis tasks which have to be done before any further high-level analysis tasks. We present a novel algorithm which does all these analysis tasks in an unified way, by utilizing a combination of inter-frame and intra-frame measures derived from the motion field and normalized cross correlation. The algorithm runs four times faster than real-time due to sparse and selective calculation of these measures.

Index Terms— video analysis, shot detection, sampling structure detection, keyframe detection, real-time analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to perform high-level computer vision tasks (like object detection and tracking) on video content, first some fundamental preprocessing tasks have to be performed in advance. Specifically, the content has to be split into individual shots (shot boundary detection), which are usually separated by hardcuts or short dissolves.

It is also crucial to detect the sampling structure of the video. The sampling structure can be progressive, interlaced (each frame contains two fields of half width which are from consecutive timepoints) or 3:2 pulldown (the standard method for converting progressive film content with 24 frames per second to interlaced video content with 60 fields per second). For example, for an interlaced video it is not advisable to use the whole frame, as it will exhibit combing artifacts if motion is present in the scene (as the two fields are from different timepoints). For interlaced video, the information about the field order (which can be upper field first or lower field first) is also desired.

Finally, for extracting an image dataset for training neural networks from an video an algorithm for the extraction of dynamic keyframes is needed. Dynamic keyframes are non-uniformly spaced frames which adapt to the variation in the video. In video segments with high variation (e.g. fast motion scene) more keyframes will be extracted, whereas in a static video segment the spacing between the keyframe will be much larger.

Despite the practical importance of these fundamental video analysis tasks, not a lot of research is devoted to this area (although there are a few patents). For example, for sampling structure detection only a few works (like [1] and [2]) have been proposed in the literature. Addressing this, we propose a novel method which does shot detection, sampling structure detection and dynamic keyframe extraction in an unified way. Due to the unified approach and sparse and selective calculation of the content-based measures, it is able to run four times faster than real-time. In the following, we give an outline of our proposed algorithm.

2. ALGORITHM

All components of our proposed algorithm rely on the following measures:

- $AMM(I, J)$ is the average magnitude of the motion vectors of the motion field calculated between the images I and J . For calculating the motion field, we employ the *Dense Inverse Search* optical flow algorithm from [3]. It runs very fast employing only the CPU and is quite robust against brightness variations. It works well also for large motion in the scene (e.g. sports videos), which is especially important for the shot detection component.
- $SWR(I, J)$ is the image dissimilarity between the *reference* image I and the warped (motion-compensated) J . The warped image is generated by calculating the motion field between both images and warping the image J with the motion field. When the motion compensation works properly, then the warped image should be identical to the reference image. We employ the normalised cross correlation (NCC) similarity measure in order to be invariant against brightness variations due to flicker or camera flashlights.
- $ACT(I, J)$ is the geometric average of $AMM(I, J)$ and $SWR(I, J)$ and measures the *activity* between the images I and J . If the images are very similar and there is not a lot a motion between them, $ACT(I, J)$ will be nearly zero, whereas in the opposite case its value will be high.

The activity between consecutive video frames $ACT(I_t, I_{t+1})$ is calculated always. All other measures $ACT(I_t, I_s)$ are calculate sparsely and selectively, only if they are beneficial to verify a certain hypothesis (e.g. the hypothesis that the current shot is interlaced). We employ a framework where measures are calculated on-demand and cached, in order to ensure that two algorithms components (e.g. shot detector and dynamic keyframes detector) do not calculate the same measure twice.

The **shot detector** comprises two phases. The first phase (fast check) does for each frame a check whether it is possible that at this frame a hardcut or short dissolve (consisting of up to 4 frames) occurs. As the first phase is done for every frame, it must be very fast. The second phase (deep check) is only invoked if the first phase decides that at this frame it is possible that a short dissolve occurs. It tests for each $K \in 1..4$ whether the hypothesis of a K -frame dissolve at this frame is valid or not (note that $K = 1$ denotes a hardcut). The second phase is not invoked very often and therefore can be computationally much more expensive without impacting the overall runtime negatively. A hypothesis for a K - frame dissolve is verified if the activity $ACT(I_t, I_{t-j})$ between the last frame I_t before the dissolve and its predecessors I_{t-j} is significantly smaller than the activity $ACT(I_t, I_{t+K})$ between the last frame before the dissolve and the first frame after it. This makes sense, as the activity $ACT(I_t, I_{t+K})$ will be high if the frames I_t and I_{t+K} are from different shots.

The **sampling structure detector** utilizes a combination of inter-frame and intra-frame activity measures. Each frame I_t is split into its upper field I_t^u and lower field I_t^l , then we calculate the three basic measures $v_0 = ACT(I_t^u, I_t^l)$, $v_1 = ACT(I_t^u, I_{t+1}^l)$ and $v_2 = ACT(I_t^l, I_{t+1}^u)$. Each sampling structure type has now a very characteristic pattern in the relation of the measures v_0 , v_1 and v_2 . *Progressive content* is characterized by a near-zero value of v_0 , whereas the values v_1 and v_2 are non-zero and approximately equal. *Interlaced content* is characterized by nonzero values of v_0 , v_1 and v_2 . Furthermore, the values v_1 and v_2 are *not* approximately equal, because one corresponds to fields which are significantly further apart in time. For 3 : 2 *pulldown*, the pattern is more complex, as it depends also on the position of the frame within a *pulldown unit* consisting of 5 frames. By analyzing several frames of the shot statistically, we can determine now whether its sampling structure is progressive, interlaced or 3 : 2 pulldown.

The principle of the **dynamic keyframe detector** is straightforward. Within a shot, we are accumulating the activity values $ACT(I_t, I_{t+q})$ between consecutive frames. If the accumulated sum is higher than a certain threshold, then we trigger a keyframe for the current frame and set the accumulated sum back to zero.

A qualitative evaluation shows that our proposed algorithm works well also for challenging content, e.g. with fast motion or brightness variations like flicker or camera flashlights.

Fig. 1. Screenshot of demo application.

3. DEMO APPLICATION

The demo application is a mixed C++ / Python application, which runs on a Intel PC. The core algorithm has been implemented in C++ and runs solely on the CPU. In order to make the algorithm available in Python, a Python wrapper has been developed for it with the *pybind11*¹ package. The demo application (see Figure 1) opens a video, runs the algorithm on it and shows the detection results. The dynamic keyframes are shown in a separate window as soon as they are detected. The result of the shot and sampling structure detector (progressive / interlaced / pulldown) for the *previous* shot is overlaid as text onto the window showing the input video. Naturally, the shot boundary can be only detected for the *previous* shot, as for the current shot it is still to be determined. The algorithm runs approximately four times faster than real-time (on average 11 ms per frame), but the playback in the demo application has been slowed down so that the video is shown in normal playing speed.

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4. REFERENCES

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¹<https://pypi.org/project/pybind11/>